

Using single-site augering to determine root distribution of rice

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Simple auger sampling method is generally used to determine root distribution of field-grown plants. We formulated and tested a method for determining average root mass density (RMD) of rice using single-site sampling (SSS). Root data were obtained from experiments on N and green manure effects on rice in loamy sand and sandy loam soils at PAU Research Farm, Ludhiana. Plots were puddled by disking twice followed by planking in standing water. Six-wk-old rice seedlings of cultivar PR106 were transplanted in mid-June 1992 at 15- × 20-cm spacing.

Roots were sampled by monolith excavation and by auger at 20, 40, and 75 d after transplanting (DT). Because rice seedlings were inserted 5 cm below the soil surface during transplanting, the 0-5 cm soil layer contained no roots and was removed before sampling. Soil monoliths (10 cm toward midrow × 15 cm along the

Estimated position for centering the auger and root mean square deviation (RMSD) of root mass density (RMD) for different sampling schemes at different plant growth stages.

Stage	Treatment	Soil layer (cm)	R ²	Av RMD (D ^Δ) (mg/cm ³)	Estimated position for centering the auger (cm)	RMSD				
						A	B	C	(A+B)/2	
<i>Loamy sand</i>										
20 DT	N (60 kg/ha)	5-15	0.88 ^{*b}	0.22	3.1	0.79	0.47	0.12	0.11	
	N (120 kg/ha)	5-15	0.93 [*]	0.22	3.5	0.50	0.24	0.04	0.05	
	GM ^a	5-15	0.91 [*]	0.32	3.6	0.35	0.28	0.09	0.10	
40 DT	N (60 kg/ha)	5-15	0.98 [*]	0.38	3.5	0.27	0.44	0.11	0.10	
		15-25	0.42	0.05	3.0	0.30	0.10	0.03	0.04	
	N (120 kg/ha)	5-15	0.99 [*]	0.90	3.5	0.34	0.22	0.15	0.12	
		15-25	0.67 [*]	0.03	3.8	0.30	0.04	0.05	0.07	
	GM	5-15	0.98 [*]	0.65	3.4	0.25	0.32	0.13	0.14	
		15-25	0.82 [*]	0.07	4.0	0.10	0.12	0.02	0.02	
75 DT	N (60 kg/ha)	5-15	0.91 [*]	0.61	3.1	0.32	0.74	0.15	0.10	
		15-25	0.58	0.08	3.5	0.15	0.21	0.05	0.09	
		25-35	0.90 [*]	0.03	3.2	0.10	0.15	0.07	0.04	
	N (120 kg/ha)	5-15	0.99 [*]	1.09	3.5	0.49	0.50	0.10	0.12	
		15-25	0.36	0.08	3.0	0.19	0.17	0.08	0.10	
		25-35	0.93 [*]	0.04	3.6	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.04	
	GM	5-15	0.99 [*]	1.27	3.4	0.45	0.38	0.08	0.04	
		15-25	0.97 [*]	0.13	3.0	0.15	0.08	0.17	0.13	
		25-35	0.93 [*]	0.06	3.7	0.11	0.05	0.08	0.10	
	<i>Sandy loam</i>									
	20 DT	N (60 kg/ha)	5-15	0.97 [*]	0.26	3.3	0.85	0.69	0.13	0.11
		N (120 kg/ha)	5-15	0.98 [*]	0.28	3.4	0.43	0.09	0.10	0.11
GM		5-15	0.97 [*]	0.30	3.4	0.10	0.13	0.09	0.07	
40 DT	N (60 kg/ha)	5-15	0.98 [*]	0.49	3.5	0.43	0.51	0.18	0.21	
		15-25	0.81 [*]	0.07	4.0	0.11	0.19	0.10	0.15	
	N (120 kg/ha)	5-15	0.99 [*]	0.94	3.5	0.33	0.27	0.13	0.07	
		15-25	0.82 [*]	0.09	4.0	0.14	0.17	0.11	0.07	
	GM	5-15	0.92 [*]	0.74	3.5	0.65	0.35	0.13	0.14	
		15-25	0.81 [*]	0.14	3.2	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.03	
75 DT	N (60 kg/ha)	5-15	0.90 [*]	0.70	3.1	0.71	0.33	0.15	0.11	
		15-25	0.58	0.18	3.7	0.33	0.21	0.10	0.05	
		25-35	0.90 [*]	0.13	3.0	0.12	0.11	0.09	0.07	
	N (120 kg/ha)	5-15	0.99 [*]	1.28	3.6	0.59	0.41	0.09	0.09	
		15-25	0.82 [*]	0.18	3.2	0.10	0.11	0.05	0.04	
		25-35	0.99 [*]	0.08	3.3	0.05	0.10	0.05	0.05	
	GM	5-15	0.97 [*]	1.29	3.4	0.55	0.28	0.16	0.12	
		15-25	0.98 [*]	0.25	3.5	0.19	0.15	0.05	0.07	
		25-35	0.98 [*]	0.09	3.2	0.12	0.10	0.04	0.07	

^aGM = green manure. ^b* = significant at P = 0.05.

row × 10 cm deep) were excavated to a depth of 35 cm in four replications. Each monolith was sectioned vertically in five 2-cm-thick segments (see figure). Soil from each segment was washed on a 1-mm mesh screen. Roots were cleaned

Sampling schemes for monolith excavations and single-site augering.^a

^aa* = plant.

and dried at 60 °C to constant weight. RMD was calculated as mg roots/cm³ soil and regressed against horizontal distance (d) from the plant base using a polynomial function. Average RMD (D^Δ) was computed by integrating the polynomial fitted to the horizontal root distribution (RMD f[d]) in the unit soil strip and dividing it by distance between two limits.

$$D^{\Delta} = 1/10 \int_0^{10} \text{RMD } f(d)$$

The $D^{\wedge}$ in each layer and treatment was interpolated on the horizontal root distribution curve to determine the center for single-site augering (see table). For a given soil layer, RMD determined by centering a 5-cm-diam auger using this sampling scheme (C in figure) was compared with other possible single-site sampling schemes (A and B in figure). Auger samples were collected from nine replications for all schemes. Reliability of a sampling scheme was assessed from root mean square of differences in RMD with the given scheme from $D^{\wedge}$.

RMD was greatest close to the plant base and decreased with increasing distance to a point. Then RMD increased again due to contribution of roots from

the adjacent row. RMD distribution for all treatments and stages followed the same pattern. A quadratic polynomial generally best explained the relationship between horizontal root distribution and distance.

The position for centering the auger for SSS, computed from interpolation of $D^{\wedge}$ on the horizontal root distribution curve, was between 3 and 4 cm from the plant box for both soils irrespective of sampling stage and treatment (see table).

When compared with other SSS methods, RMD determination using scheme C resulted in minimum root mean square deviation (RMSD) from $D^{\wedge}$. RMSD of scheme (A + B)/2 was comparable with scheme C, but sampling

at two sites requires more labor and time and is highly destructive.

Results suggest the horizontal root distribution in the top 10-cm soil layer may be sufficient for determining the sampling site for centering the auger. In puddled and flooded soils, a small ring should be hammered around the sampling site a day before sampling and the water removed from within.

Single-site augering estimates of RMD are very close to those of monolith excavations. The simplicity and precision of the single-site auger method allows more replications and rapidity of sampling—with reduced labor and destruction of experimental plots—than do other methods. ■

News about research collaboration

IRRI guidelines encourage marketing of hybrid rice seed to farmers

Farmers in developing countries will pay for hybrid rice seed—if it benefits them at harvest.

A policy statement by the IRRI Board of Trustees makes all breeding lines, elite germplasm, and parental lines produced by the Institute's breeding program freely available to both public and private organizations. IRRI's hybrid rice materials will be provided to national agricultural research systems for their use and for sharing with private organizations in their countries.

"IRRI recognizes that the private sector is likely to play an important role in developing hybrid rice technology," says S. S. Virmani, an IRRI plant breeder who specializes in hybrid rice. "To expedite the process of getting hybrid rice seed to farmers, IRRI realized the need to have guidelines to govern the distribution of IRRI hybrid materials."

The Institute will not seek intellectual property protection (patents) for its rice breeding materials. IRRI expects recognition, however for the use of its materials when a hybrid rice variety is released.

Virmani believes that the value-added benefits of hybrid rice—just like hybrid maize and cotton—will make the technology attractive to both farmers and seed companies.

IRRI's policy on intellectual property rights and hybrid rice is as follows:

- IRRI adheres to the policy of free availability of breeding lines, elite germplasm, and parental lines produced in its breeding program and will not seek intellectual property protection on these materials.
- IRRI will provide hybrid rice parental lines (and other elite materials) to both public sector

institutions and private organizations on the understanding that a) the material is not intended for exclusive use by any single organization, b) IRRI retains the right to distribute the same material to other organizations, and c) the use of IRRI materials will be recognized when a hybrid rice variety is released.

- Collaboration with profit-making organizations for the development of hybrid rice technology will proceed after consultation, where appropriate, with the authorities in the respective host country. ■

Thai farmers like mechanized harvesting system

Farmers in northeastern Thailand may soon be harvesting their rice faster—with fewer workers and less expense.

Serious labor shortages at harvest are increasing costs to farmers in some Asian countries. At the same time, rice prices are declining. IRRI agricultural engineers have been developing efficient mechanized rice harvesting systems for small farms to reduce harvest costs.

Researchers from IRRI and the Agricultural Engineering Division of the

Thai Department of Agriculture field-tested the IRRI-designed stripper gatherer harvesting system on small farms near Khon Kaen. The farmers liked the machine's maneuverability. Its 80-cm working width efficiently harvested both lodged and erect rice on small plots; farmers agreed that the grain loss was acceptably low.

"Farmers were most impressed by the machine's ability to harvest and thresh simultaneously," says Boru Douthwaite, a consultant in the IRRI Agricultural Engineering Division. Farmers have been suffering severe grain losses due to